

Construction of Fluorinated Organoboron Compounds (CARGO)

Version 0

Description

Fluorinated organoboron compounds are important synthetic building blocks that display the unique characteristics of a fluorinated motif with the versatile synthetic applications of organoboron moiety. Although such compounds are very valuable in various fields, such as pharmaceuticals and materials science, the types of fluorine-containing organoboron compounds are not abundant and their synthetic methods are also very limited. CARGO aims to develop a “toolbox” for both boryl-fluoromethylation and fluoromethylation of simple activated organic molecules by utilizing a bifunctional reagent, gem-diborylfluoromethane that can undergo a wide range of carbon-carbon bond-forming reactions by both catalytic and non-catalytic processes. Given its chemical stability and synthetic versatility, gem-diborylfluoromethane is deemed as an attractive reagent for constructing compounds with molecular complexity (containing both fluorine and boron moieties). Investigations will be carried out to explore the synthetic potential of this new reagent by developing sustainable synthetic approaches to access fluorinated organoboron compounds via radical and nucleophilic routes. Methodologies developed within the project will be validated on biologically relevant targets for medicinal and drug discovery purposes.

Funder

Central Finance and Contracting Agency

Grant

Resilience Facility (RRF)
(5.2.1.1.i.)

Researchers

Nagarajan Ramkumar (orcid:0000-0002-6452-532X)

Organizations
Institute of Organic Synthesis

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Construction of Fluorinated Organoboron Compounds \(CARGO\)](#)

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Fluorinated organoboron compounds are important synthetic building blocks that display the unique characteristics of a fluorinated motif with the versatile synthetic applications of organoboron moiety. Although such compounds are very valuable in various fields, such as pharmaceuticals and materials science, the types of fluorine-containing organoboron compounds are not abundant and their synthetic methods are also very limited. CARGO aims to develop a “toolbox” for both boryl-fluoromethylation and fluoromethylation of simple activated organic molecules by utilizing a bifunctional reagent, gem-diborylfluoromethane that can undergo a wide range of carbon-carbon bond-forming reactions by both catalytic and non-catalytic processes. Given its chemical stability and synthetic versatility, gem-diborylfluoromethane is deemed as an attractive reagent for constructing compounds with molecular complexity (containing both fluorine and boron moieties). Investigations will be carried out to explore the synthetic potential of this new reagent by developing sustainable synthetic approaches to access fluorinated organoboron compounds via radical and nucleophilic routes. Methodologies developed within the project will be validated on biologically relevant targets for medicinal and drug discovery purposes.

Researchers:

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Organizations:

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Contact: [Nagarajan Ramkumar](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Central Finance and Contracting Agency](#)

Grants: [Resilience Facility \(RRF\) \(5.2.1.1.i.\)](#)

Project: [Resilience Facility \(RRF\) \(5.2.1.1.i.\)](#)

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Experimental procedures, analytical data and reporting

Data collected will be of distinct origin: laboratory protocols of chemical synthesis, analytical data; characterization of chemical compounds. Besides the research specific data there will be project management and reporting data.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of collecting and generating data is directly linked to the aim and objectives of the project. During this project, new reagent and synthetic methodologies will be developed to achieve fluorinated organoboron compounds of medicinal interest. For this purpose experimental descriptions of chemical synthesis, analytical data and characterization of compounds will be generated.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- txt
- html
- pdf
- tiff
- png
- xls
- jpg
- others

Data gathered will typically be in the following formats: MS Excel (.xls*), MS Word (.doc*), MS PowerPoint (.ppt*), Comma Separated Values (.csv), Portable Document Format (.pdf), Joint Photographic Experts Group(.jpg), Tagged Image File Format (.tiff), sequence (.fasq.gz, fastq), ELN files (.pdf), Bead View software files(.lxout), SoftMax Pro Data file (.pda), SPSS statistics data document (.sav). R Software files (.R, .RData), plain text files (.txt), Adobe Photoshop files (.PSD/.PDD), Leica LAS AF Lite (.lif), RAW Format (.raw), C++ (.cpp), Matlab (.m), Python (.py), MeVisLab(.mlab); literature reference files (RIS, enl, Bib(La)Tex, MODS); chemical data base (.cfx). Equipment specific data files, for instance, mass spectrometry, NMR, will be generated along with formats mentioned above. These files will have proprietary formats defined by equipment vendors.

1.1.4 Expected size of the data - give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

id: null, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will be re-used by reporting, writing the publications, patent applications, and project applications.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

The extent of metadata will correspond to the specific requirements of experiment and applied technique, however at least the following information

shall be available:

- author name
- date of the experiment
- format of the data

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

organofluorine compounds, organoboron reagents, nucleophilic and radical reactions, sustainable technologies, drug discovery

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will remain closed by default.

Rationale: All data obtained during the project will remain closed for the protection of the Intellectual Property Rights and to allow for patenting of compounds, technologies and assays

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo period for generated data will depend whether the data will be disclosed to public in a form of scientific publication or research conference or if the generated data warrens IP protection. The issues related to IP protection will be discussed with our patent and technology transfer office

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

Data will be stored in data storages within institution LIOS. Free archive services such as chemRxiv will be used for preprints of research manuscripts. Whenever appropriate, the data will be deposited in publicly accessible databases. LIOS will follow internal policies when choosing repositories.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

For most data, no special software is needed and standard programs (Windows Office, ChemOffice) are sufficient to access and (re-)analyze the data. For certain cases, especially data generated by research equipment either specialized software or proprietary software provided by the vendor of the equipment is needed (SU: out file software: winscp (windows), and scp (for Macintosh linux)); MestreNova for NMR data, Waters HPLC data; Pymol; Shroedinger suite, Datawarrior, XCalibur and TraceFinder for MS data.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

No, all the data can be retrieved using commercial/open access software, in case of doubt instrument manuals should be applied.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

After publication of the results, interoperability of the data will become possible by publishing in supplementary files of the publication. Raw data files could be obtained upon request.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Indicate the license planned to use

The different possibilities to out-license data, knowledge and IP generated in the project will be discussed with LIOS deputy director and patent and technology transfer office.

Possibilities for licensing include:

- 1) Know-how transfer
- 2) licensing of IP as part of a research & Development project with an industrial partner (milestone payments)
- 3) licensing of IP to third party

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

All results and know how generated by the project will be evaluated by project leader and if needed, discussed with patent and technology transfer office . Primarily, data generated during this project will be disseminated in scientific forums (conferences, publications). If the data will be related to results of commercialization potential, foreground IP created by the project will only be released after official approval from the PCT, European and/or US patent agency has been obtained (depending on the protection strategy pursuit).

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Access to project results will be available at least 5 years after project at the partner data storage.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Data quality assurance policies established at LIOS will be followed.

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The costs of the licenses of software will be paid from the infrastructure maintenance budget.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The long term data preservation is subject to data management policies of LIOS.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Data security and storage is provided by LIOS IT departement

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

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